

IMPACT OF INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY ON INTRA-REGIONAL TRADE FLOWS IN ECOWAS COUNTRIES

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Abstract: *This study examined the impact of institutional quality on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS. The main objective of this research is to critically examine the effect of institutional quality on trade in ECOWAS from 2010 to 2023 using the gravity model of trade. Panel Unit Root tests were employed to test for stationarity of the series. Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood Fixed Effect (PPML), was employed to test further for a long-run relationship. The results reveal that the institutional quality index at the aggregated level has an insignificant and positive impact on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS. The analysis of the disaggregated indices shows positive and significant effects of all three (voice and accountability, regulatory quality, and rule of law) out of six indices on intra-regional trade, while political stability, government effectiveness, and control of corruption have a negative but significant impact on trade. Furthermore, we find that gross domestic product and gross domestic product per capita are positively correlated with trade but are insignificant. The results, however, revealed that population growth has a negative but significant effect on trade in ECOWAS. The traditional gravity model variables (GDP, population, distance, landlocked, and official common language) are found to be important factors for bilateral trade flows. The study recommends that policymakers in ECOWAS should improve their institutional frameworks to combat corruption, political instability, and enhance government effectiveness through measures such as relaxed licensing requirements, reduced import taxes, and other bureaucratic bottlenecks.*

Keywords: *ECOWAS, Institutional, Intra-Regional, Quality, Trade.*

1.1 Introduction

Trade is often regarded as a critical engine of economic growth and development. Trade, by promoting the cross-border interchange of products and services, can promote productivity, foster innovation, and increase competitiveness (Shu & Steinwender, 2019). International trade, however, plays a vital role in promoting economic development and progress by raising income levels. According to Muhammad, Imran, Naila, and Muhammad (2018), a lot of economies are opening up and embracing economic integration in order to improve the economy and raise living standards. For the continent to see

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sustained growth, intra-African commerce must be encouraged (Whelsy, Francis, & Amara, 2022). The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) was created in 1975 and authorized by the Treaty of Lagos with the aim of fostering collaboration and integration among its member states and improving trade outcomes among West African countries. Trade and market integration through the creation of a customs union to foster swift growth and development among member states is at the core of ECOWAS. However, domestic economic institutions and the regional integration process must complement each other in order for an economic union to be formed (Ojeaga et al., 2014; Anowor, Ichoku & Onodugo, 2020; Ochinanwata et al, 2020). ECOWAS came into existence with the shared objective of fostering political stability and economic growth and has successfully managed to solve shared problems and strengthen cooperation among its 15 member nations. By creating various programs and processes, ECOWAS has played a significant role in fleshing out regional integration throughout the years, providing a platform for member nations to foster cooperative activities towards economic growth.

Understanding the ECOWAS trade relations dynamic is important in ascertaining the economic development and institutional quality of the region. Therefore, there is a need to understand the interplay between institutional quality and trade in attempting to fashion policies that will promote sustainable and equitable development within the ECOWAS region. However, regional integration is generally viewed by politicians and scholars in Africa as a way to enhance intraregional trade, economic expansion, and make nations firmly establish themselves in the world economy. Regional integration can also help African nations accelerate the transformation of their economies through the agglomeration of economies of scale, productivity, mobilization of capital, and regional value chains.

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) is a regional grouping consisting of 15 West African countries with the vision of regional integration and economic development (Inaju-Challydoff, 2024; Agbarakwe et al, 2018). The member states of ECOWAS have developed some policies and programs over time with the objective of developing trade, improving institutional quality, and supporting economic growth. These are presented in the form of trade liberalization measures (Bankole et al., 2012), institutional reforms (Basiru & Osunkoya, 2017), infrastructure development (CEDERO ECOWAS, 2018), and policies with a focus on specific sectors (Bamoi & Yilmaz, 2021). These notwithstanding, the region remains beset by weak institutional frameworks, underdeveloped infrastructure, and susceptibility to external shocks (Diallo et al., 2022).

1.2 Statement of the problem

Despite several regional initiatives, including the Common External Tariff (CET) and the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS), intra-ECOWAS trade is surprisingly low, accounting for only 12–15% of regional trade, far below levels seen in other regional blocs like the European Union and ASEAN

(Nwonye et al, 2023; Banga et al., 2021; Nwonye et al, 2020). This ongoing poor performance raises questions about ECOWAS's policy ability to advance regional trade integration.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to examine the impact of institutional quality on trade among ECOWAS countries. The specific objectives are to:

- i. To assess the impact of institutional quality on intra-regional trade in the ECOWAS region.
- ii. To examine whether institutional quality facilitates or hinders the effectiveness of intra-regional trade in the ECOWAS region.
- iii. To ascertain the direction of causal relationships between institutional quality and intra-regional trade in the ECOWAS region.

1.4 Hypotheses of the study

The following null hypotheses will be tested:

- i. **H₀₁**: Institutional quality has no significant impact on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS member states.
- ii. **H₀₂**: Institutional quality does not facilitate intra-regional trade among ECOWAS member states.
- iii. **H₀₃**: There is no causal relationship between institutional quality and intra-regional trade in ECOWAS countries.

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Institutional Quality

Efficiency, stability, and integrity are characteristics of institutions that influence social, political, and economic relations within a nation. It includes things like the rule of law, anti-corruption measures, regulatory quality, government efficiency, political stability, and accountability and voice (World Bank, 2023). Today's institutional quality measures would typically include indices such as the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), having dimensions such as government effectiveness, regulatory quality, control of corruption, and rule of law (Kaufmann, Kraay, & Mastruzzi, 2010). Additional investment is attracted to the nations with higher institutional quality, with better public services and increased government trust (OECD, 2022).

The six main dimensions of the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) are: Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence, and Control of Corruption. High-quality institutions are essential for economic development, social cohesion, and the protection of individual rights. According to North (1990), institutions are the "rules of the game" in a society – both formal (laws, constitutions) and informal (norms, traditions). Institutional quality, therefore, is not just about the presence of

institutions, but how well they function. For instance, two countries may have similar legal frameworks on paper, but if one lacks enforcement and suffers from corruption, the quality of its institutions is considerably lower. The World Bank defines institutions as "sets of formal and informal rules governing the actions of individuals and organizations, as well as the interaction of participants in the development process" (2021).

The fundamental aspects of institutional quality include voice and accountability, government efficacy, regulatory quality, political stability, rule of law, and corruption control (World Bank, 2023). High-quality institutions are essential for ensuring the enforcement of contracts, property rights protection, public service delivery, and policy credibility. According to North (1990), institutions are "the rules of the game" in a society, shaping the incentives of political and economic actors. Institutional quality thus determines the quality with which these rules are designed and applied. Empirical experience across the past decades has emphasized the central role of institutional quality in providing sustainable development, poverty decline, and enhanced economic performance (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; World Bank, 2023).

2.1.2. Intra-regional Trade

Intra-regional trade can be defined as the trade in goods and services among countries located in the same geographical region. It can be viewed as a measure of the degree to which member states in a particular economic union trade among themselves as opposed to trading with outsiders. Intra-regional trade can be viewed as a tool for improving economic integration, development, expansion, and self-reliance (Anowor & Agbarakwe, 2015). The mechanism is essential for economic integration, regional growth, and insulation from external economic shocks. Through greater economic cooperation, intra-regional trade can help produce diversified economies, improved infrastructure, and more intense political cooperation. Regional trade, or intra-regional trade, is the trade of goods, services, and capital between countries that share their borders or are close to each other geographically. Its aim is to enhance economic integration and cooperation that facilitates the ease of the free movement of goods, services, and investments within a given region. Intra-regional trade can occur through a number of mechanisms, such as:

Regional Trade Agreements (RTAs): These are agreements among nations to reduce trade restrictions, such as tariffs and quotas, in order to promote trade within an area. North American Free Trade Agreements (NAFTA), the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), and the European Union (EU) are examples of RTAs. **Common Markets and Customs Unions:** These are more advanced forms of integration, where countries within a region not only remove trade barriers but also set common external tariffs and have greater cooperation in such fields as labor markets and services. The EU is a

classic example. Trade Liberalization: Reduction or elimination of trade barriers and tariffs to facilitate more convenient trade in an area.

2.1.2. Institutional Quality Facilitates

Institutional quality has a critical role to play in the promotion of economic performance, governance efficiency, and development sustainability. Institutional quality can be defined as the quality of the effective economic and social interaction that occurs in a country through its legal, regulatory, and administrative frameworks. A country with high-quality institutions has a rule of law, control of corruption, government effectiveness, quality of regulation, political stability, and accountability. Douglass North (1990) described institutions as “the rules of the game” that shape human interaction to minimize uncertainty in economic interaction. When the quality of institutions is high, transaction costs are reduced, which makes economic exchange easy, thereby promoting economic performance. Countries with good law and order and low levels of corruption tend to have more FDI and trade activity. Empirical studies have found that trade performance and regional integration are strongly influenced by the level of regulatory quality and government effectiveness (Rodrik et al., 2004). Good customs management practices, transparent taxation policies, and sound macroeconomic policies also support trade activities between nations. In the African situation, the effectiveness of regional efforts such as the African Continental Free Trade Area is largely contingent on the institutional strength of member states to ensure compliance with rules and accountability. The lack of strong institutions, on the other hand, is associated with policy instability, corruption, and inefficiency, which are trade facilitation and economic cooperation challenges.

In addition, institutional quality is important in the facilitation of sustainable development through the enhancement of political stability. Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) posit that inclusive institutions, such as the enforcement of property rights, equality of opportunities, and the promotion of citizen participation, are important in the enhancement of long-term economic prosperity. Therefore, where institutions are either extractive or weak, the economy is likely to stagnate, leading to insecurity and lack of confidence in the institutions. As such, the enhancement of institutional quality through governance reforms, anti-corruption policies, judicial independence, and administrative efficiency is important in the enhancement of trade, growth, and regional development.

2.2. Theoretical Review

Trade theories have conventionally emphasized the concepts of comparative advantage, factor endowments, and market efficiency, while newer approaches to trade theory have come to appreciate the significance of institutional quality in influencing trade patterns. The New Institutional Economics (NIE) approach argues that institutions, which are understood to be the formal and informal rules that regulate economic activities, can help to lower transaction costs, ensure contract enforcement, and

facilitate the movement of goods and services across national borders (North, 1990). In the specific context of international trade, institutions that are characterized by features such as a clear and transparent legal system, a robust regulatory framework, and the protection of property rights are critical in facilitating market exchange and regional economic integration. North (1990) has argued that the presence of good institutions can improve the efficiency of trade by reducing the uncertainties that are associated with market exchange.

The Institutional Quality Trade Theory, based on the NIE approach, claims that trade performance does not depend on comparative advantage or resource endowments; rather, trade is also influenced by the quality of institutional arrangements (Iloafunsi & Anowor, 2026; Rodrik et al., 2004). Good institutional arrangements can help in promoting trade through the enforcement of contracts, low levels of corruption, and transparent customs procedures. Empirical studies have confirmed that countries with better institutional arrangements have higher intra-regional and extra-regional trade compared to those with poor institutional arrangements, which may lead to trade diversion.

Moreover, the theory of institutional development by Douglass North shows the relationship between the development of institutions and economic performance. In the context of trade, the theory shows that nations with effective institutions are better placed to take part in global value chains, regional trade, and benefit from trade liberalization efforts (North, 1990; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). For instance, the effective implementation of trade agreements such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) largely depends on the institutional ability of member states to harmonize policies, enforce policies, and settle any differences that may arise.

3. Methodology

This study adopts an Ex post facto research design, a type of non-experimental research that is widely used in the social sciences when investigators examine causal relationships among variables that have already occurred. Annual data of bilateral trade of fifteen (15) ECOWAS countries Nigeria, Ghana, Niger, Benin, Burkina Faso, Mali, Guinea Bissau, Guinea, Cabo Verde, Liberia, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo, The Gambia and Cote d'Ivoire were employed over the period of 2010-2023. Data were extracted from World Bank development indicator Database, 2023. The data were analysis using econometric software such as Stata.

The Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimation technique is employed in this study to estimate the gravity model of trade. The PPML estimator has several advantages when analyzing trade flows. First, it effectively handles the problem of heteroscedasticity, which commonly occurs in trade data and can bias traditional estimation techniques. Second, the method allows the inclusion of zero trade flows that often exist between some trading partners. This is particularly important when studying trade in developing regions where some countries may not trade with each other in certain

periods. Third, the PPML estimator ensures that the estimated coefficients are consistent and reliable when fixed effects are included in the model.

The choice of PPML is also justified by the characteristics of intra-regional trade in Africa, where a significant proportion of bilateral trade flows may record zero values. The estimator therefore provides more efficient and unbiased results compared with traditional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation.

Model Specification

The study adopts the standard gravity model of international trade to analyze the determinants of intra-regional trade flows among ECOWAS countries. The gravity model explains trade flows between two countries based on their economic sizes and the distance between them, while also incorporating other trade-related factors.

The general gravity model is specified as follows:

$$X_{ij,t} = \frac{G_t(\pi_{i,t}\Phi_{j,t})}{T_{ij,t}} \forall i, j \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

- $X_{ij,t}$ Represents the value of exports and imports from country i to country j at time t.
- $T_{ij,t}$ Denotes all bilateral trade frictions between country i and country j, which may include transportation costs, trade barriers, and other transaction costs.
- $\pi_{i,t}$ And $\Phi_{j,t}$ represent the characteristics of the exporting and importing countries respectively, such as economic size and other country-specific factors.
- G_t Represents a gravity constant that reflects the overall level of global economic activity at time t.

To estimate the model empirically, the equation is transformed into a linear form by taking the natural logarithm of the variables. The log-linearized form of the model is expressed as:

$$\ln X_{ij,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln Y_{i,t} + \alpha_2 \ln Y_{j,t} + \alpha_3 \ln T_{ij,t} + \alpha_4 \ln \Pi_i + \alpha_5 \ln P_j + \mu_{ij,t} \quad (3.4)$$

For the purpose of this study, the model is extended to include institutional quality, which represents the key variable of interest in examining its effect on intra-regional trade flows within ECOWAS. The extended gravity model used in this study is therefore specified as follows:

$$\ln trade_{ij,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln GDP_{i,t} + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{j,t} + \beta_3 \ln GDPpc_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln GDPpc_{j,t} + \beta_5 POP_{i,t} + \beta_6 POP_{j,t} + \beta_7 \ln inst_{i,t} + \beta_8 \ln inst_{j,t} + \beta_9 landlock_i + \beta_{10} landlock_j + \beta_{11} \ln Dist_{ij} + \beta_{12} lang_i + \beta_{13} lang_j + \varepsilon_{ij,t} \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

- **ln** = Natural logarithm
- **trade** = the value of exports and imports from country i to country j at time t

- **GDP** = Gross Domestic Product, representing the productive and consumption capacity that determines trade flows between countries i and j
- **GDPpc** = Gross Domestic Product per capita, which reflects the level of economic development and allows comparison of prosperity among ECOWAS countries with different population sizes
- **POP** = population of the two countries i and j at time t, representing market size
- **inst** = institutional quality index of the countries involved in trade
- **landlock** = a dummy variable indicating whether a country is landlocked
- **Dist** = geographical distance between the two trading countries
- **lang** = a dummy variable indicating whether the countries share a common language
- ϵ = stochastic error term capturing other factors affecting trade flows

Panel Granger Causality: Model Specification

To further examine the direction of causality among the variables used in this study, the researcher employs a panel Granger causality test. This approach helps determine whether changes in one variable can predict changes in another variable across ECOWAS countries over time. The test is conducted within a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) framework, which allows each variable in the model to be explained by its own past values and the past values of other variables.

The panel causality test also accounts for cross-sectional heterogeneity among countries in the sample by estimating separate regressions for each cross-sectional unit. The approach therefore makes it possible to determine whether there is a causal relationship among the variables included in the study. The following system of equations is estimated:

$$\Delta Trade_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\Delta GDP_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\Delta GDPpc_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\Delta inst_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.6)$$

$$\Delta lang_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\Delta Dist_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\Delta Landlock_{i,t} = \alpha_1 + \sum_p \alpha_2 \Delta GDP_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_3 \Delta GDPpc_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_4 \Delta inst_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_5 \Delta lang_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_6 \Delta Dist_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_7 \Delta Landlock_{i,t-p} + \sum_p \alpha_8 \Delta Trade_{i,t-p} + \mu_{it} \quad (3.9)$$

Where:

- Δ = first difference operator
- i = cross-sectional units (ECOWAS countries)
- t = time period
- p = optimal lag length determined using appropriate lag selection criteria
- μ_{it} = error term capturing other factors affecting the variables

4.1. Data Presentation and Analysis

This focus of chapter will be mainly on the empirical analysis of intra-regional trade within ECOWAS nations to achieve the study’s three objectives. Furthermore, this section presents, analyses and discusses of the empirical results. The hypotheses of the study are tested against the alternatives, and conclusion drawn in this section of the study. First, the results of preliminary test were presented and discussed.

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Result of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Trade	210	59.43219	16.0266	30.42051	105.8675	.7936299	3.459041
VC	210	39.76977	16.28357	8.866995	79.121621	.593734	2.855445
RQ	210	29.94117	12.99626	8.018867	60.84906	.2973356	2.153326
PS	210	30.16506	19.39678	.4716981	80.18868	.5048356	2.663909
GOV	210	24.92827	15.38905	1.904762	66.19048	.7232317	2.623455
CORR	210	33.09684	19.14752	1.904763	82.38095	.7201792	3.064535
RULE	210	29.98885	15.89713	1.408431	75	.6760284	2.852795
IQI	210	-1.14e-09	2.189432	-3.5369	5.552706	.9049898	3.128844
GDP	210	4.559698	4.101702	-	21.07901	-1.957255	16.76641
				20.80527			
GDPpc	210	1299.605	911.6794	474.4257	4850.984	1.851043	5.968552
POP	210	2.471787	.762821	.0132719	3.92047	-1.69679	7.080297
DIS	210	193.5274	250.6572	.9951369	1554.244	2.59516	11.00168
LANDLOCK	210	.8095238	.393615	0	1	-1.576482	3.485294
LANG	210	.5333333	.5000797	0	1	-.1336306	1.017857

Source: Authors’ compilation, 2025.

4.1.2 Correlation analysis

Table 4.2 Result of Correlation analysis

	Trade	IQI	GDP	GDPpc	POP	DIST	LANDLOCK	LANG
Trade	1.0000							
IQI	0.0081	1.0000						
GDP	-	0.1385	1.0000					
	0.0560							
GDPpc	0.5958	0.0145	-	1.0000				
			0.0525					
POP	-	0.0350	0.2030	-0.7652	1.0000			
	0.6005							
DIST	-	0.1241	0.0173	0.0549	0.0318	1.0000		
	0.0208							
LANDLOCK	-	0.0154	0.0881	-0.3314	0.4802	0.0901	1.0000	
	0.0795							
LANG	0.2551	-	-0.1121	0.3369	-	0.0594	-0.4537	1.0000
		0.0262			0.4278			

Source: Authors' compilation, 2025.

The correlation matrix for every variable is shown in Table 4.2. Whether there is a positive or negative correlation between the two variables is shown by the sign of the correlation coefficient. The findings indicate a considerable positive link between intra-regional commerce and the ECOWAS countries' institutional quality score. Therefore, the strength or weakness of the link is indicated by the absolute value, independent of sign. However, since the aggregate index is not included in the same model as the six indicators, multicollinearity is not a problem. Once more, since the correlation coefficients for the other variables are less than .80, the pairwise matrix does not have any further multicollinearity problems (Varotto & Zhao, 2018). This implies that there is little to no multicollinearity among the regressors.

4.1.3 Stationarity of the Panel Series

Table 4.3 Panel Unit Root Test

Variables	Im Persaran and Shin (CIPS) Test Level Form Statistic(z-bar)	5% Critical Values	1 st Difference	Order of integration

Trade	-5.6422	-1.920	I(o)
VC	-7.7308	-1.920	I(o)
RQ	-7.0860	-1.920	1(o)
PS	-7.4775	-1.920	I(o)
GOV	-8.1067	-1.920	I(o)
CORR	-7.3060	-1.920	I(o)
RULE	-6.7289	-1.920	I(o)
IQI	-7.2935	-1.920	1(o)
GDP	-6.8536	-1.920	I(o)
GDPpc	-8.2239	-1.920	I(o)
POP	-6.8991	-1.920	I(o)
DIST	-7.3637	-1.920	I(o)
LANDLOCK	-7.5152	-1.920	1(o)
LANG	-38883	-1.920	I(o)

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

Table 4.3 presents the results of stationarity tests using the CIPS method. From the results, the variables (trade, Voice and accountability, regulatory quality, political stability, government effectiveness, control of corruption and rule of law, institutional quality index, gross domestic product, gross domestic product per capita, population growth, distance, landlock and language) were all stationary at a level form I(o), across the countries. This indicates that all of the variables utilized in the estimation are of order zero integration, I (o). Given the variables were all integrated at level form. This allows for the research to go straight for the main estimation.

4.2 Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) Estimates:

The study estimates the impact of institutional quality on trade in the ECOWAS. Analysis of intra-regional trade using aggregate institutional quality

Table 4.4 Results for PPML estimates

Variable	Coefficients	Std dev.	Z-statistic	Prob
IQI	.0032476	.0041988	0.77	0.439
GDP	.0011946	.0024391	0.49	0.624
GDPpc	.000071	.0000152	4.66	0.000
POP	-.1891955	.0218312	-8.67	0.000
DIST	-.0000652	.0000376	-1.74	0.083
LANDLOCK	.2506114	.0294153	8.52	0.000
LANG	.0534807	.0209265	2.56	0.011

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

The results in Table 4.4 present the FE-PPML aggregate estimates on the effect of institutional quality index on intra-regional trade among ECOWAS countries. Institutional quality index is found to have a positive and insignificant relationship with trade as the estimated coefficient is .0032476 at 1%. The sign of coefficient is in line with a priori expectations. This implies that aggregated institutional quality has an insignificant positive impact on trade among ECOWAS countries. Similarly, gross domestic product has a positive but insignificant impact on bilateral trade in ECOWAS countries. This indicates that a 1% increase in the economic size of one-member country raises bilateral trade by 0.003% with another member in the region.

4.2.1 Analysis on the impact of institutional quality on Intra-regional Trade in ECOWAS Using disaggregated Institutional Quality.

Table 4.5 Results for PPML estimates

Variable	Coefficients	Std dev.	Z-statistic	Prob
VC	.0072205	.0014848	4.86	0.000
RQ	.0099143	.0020308	4.88	0.000
PS	-.0027453	.0008952	-3.07	0.002
GOV	-.005881	.0017116	-3.44	0.001
CORR	-.0046395	.0014191	-3.27	0.001
RULE	.0009984	.001966	0.51	0.612
GDP	.0009714	.0024307	0.40	0.689
GDPpc	6.12e-06	.0000206	0.30	0.767
POP	-.235398	.0289133	-8.14	0.000
DIST	-.0000529	.0000373	-1.42	0.156
LANDLOCK	.1404635	.0376886	3.73	0.000
LANG	.0417464	.0224353	1.86	0.063

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

Since corruption permeates West Africa's social, cultural, and governmental structures, the outcome is hardly shocking (Transparency International report, 2017; 2018; 2019). Since of this corruption, the ECOWAS area is not a desirable place to trade since it encourages state fragility and violent conflict (Transparency International study, 2019). The institutional quality that comprises components like the rule of law, regulatory quality, corruption control, government efficacy, and political stability is a crucial but as-yet-unexplored factor of such a difficulty (Kaufmann et al., 2010). Institutions that are of good quality foster a climate that is friendly to effective trade via reduced costs of transaction, contract enforcement, and predictable and stable policy environments (Rodrik, 2008; Chang et al., 2023).

However, many ECOWAS countries continue to grapple with weak institutional structures, characterized by corruption, political instability, inefficient customs procedures, and poor enforcement of trade agreements (Eze & Ogundipe, 2022; Dollar et al., 2022). These deficiencies undermine the effectiveness of regional trade policies and discourage private sector participation in cross-border trade. While previous studies have examined the role of institutions in trade at the global level and in broader African contexts (Asiedu, 2019; Banga et al., 2021), there is a significant research gap regarding the specific relationship between institutional quality and intra-regional trade within ECOWAS countries. Most existing studies have either focused on trade volumes or broader economic performance without isolating the specific impact of institutional factors on intra-ECOWAS trade flows (Chang et al., 2023; Eze & Ogundipe, 2022). Moreover, much of the existing literature lacks recent empirical analysis that reflects the current political and economic realities within the ECOWAS region, particularly in light of global shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic and recent policy reforms.

Population growth and distance are found to have a negative but significant relationship with trade. Meanwhile, landlocked and official common language are positively related to intra-regional trade and statistically significant. This indicates that 1% rise in population growth and distance declines bilateral trade among ECOWAS countries by -0.23% and -.00005%, respectively. Also, this implies that 1% rise in landlocked and official common language increases bilateral trade among ECOWAS countries by 0.140% and .041%, respectively.

4.3 Panel Granger Causality Test

The Dumitrescu and Hurlin (2012) test was used to specify the direction of the causalities among the variables. The significance of the causality in the D–H test is determined by two types of test statistics: w-bar statistics (mean statistics for testing), z-bar information (using the standard normal distribution), and probability values.

Table 4.6: Result of panel Granger causality test

Causality	Lag values	P-value
Trade↔IQI	2	0.5888
IQI↔Trade	2	0.4901
Trade↔VC	2	0.0268
VC↔Trade	2	0.0570
Trade↔RQ	2	0.0780
RQ↔Trade	2	0.2124
Trade↔PS	2	0.0041
PS↔Trade	2	0.0744
Trade↔gov	2	0.4135

gov↔Trade	2	0.0455
Trade↔corr	2	0.6568
corr↔Trade	2	0.0329
Trade↔rule	2	0.6453
rule↔Trade	2	0.0166

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

Table 4.6 displays the results of the Panel Granger Causality test. According to the findings, the lag level is two (2). For Granger causality, a typical Chi-squared test was applied to each lag-length specification. To determine whether there is a causal route from one to another, Granger's two-way causality is then applied. As can be seen from the table, the null hypothesis that the value of the trade variable does not Granger-cause institutional quality is accepted because the p-value (0.000) is higher than the statistically significant threshold of 0.05. This indicates there is no causal relationship between intra-regional trade and the institutional quality index. However, taking a look at the causality relationship between trade and institutional quality indicators. The results show that there is a unidirectional association running from trade to voice and accountability, trade to political stability, from government effectiveness to trade, and from rule of law to trade.

4.4 Post-estimation Tests

To verify the validity of the aforementioned analysis, the overall institutional quality was broken down. In order to mitigate the endogeneity issue, we first aggregate institutional quality variables using principal component analysis. We also look at the disaggregate impact of trade-related institutional quality. This made it possible for us to investigate how each aspect of the institutional quality metrics affected intra-regional trade within ECOWAS. Due to the different institutional configurations among ECOWAS member nations, this is necessary. We use a different estimating technique to examine the robustness of our findings in order to bolster its validity. We first re-estimate our basic model using ordinary least squares (OLS), feasible generalized least squares (FGSL) and correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) techniques. Using the OLS, PCSE, and FGLS techniques serves as robustness for one another so as to observe the consistency of the impact of institutional quality on intra-regional trade among ECOWAS Countries.

Table 4.7: Results of OLS, PCSE, and FGLS estimates (Robustness Checks)

AGGREGATED

Variables	OLS	PCSE	FGLS
IQI	.170818 (0.658)	.1455087 (0.573)	.1455087 (0.699)
GDP	.0775028 (0.739)	.1553394 (0.385)	.1553394 (0.450)
GDPpc	.0049088 (0.001)	.0052785 (0.106)	.0052785
POP	-11.70311 (0.000)	-10.5869 (0.010)	10.5869 (0.000)
DIST	-.0037286 (0.282)	-.0036363 (0.349)	-.0036363 (0.271)
LANDLOCK	12.6225 (0.000)	11.90869 (0.043)	11.90869 (0.000)
LANG	2.600662 (0.000)	2.878106 (0.543)	2.878106 (0.126)
R ²	0.4647	0.4658	
Wald chi ²		34.52	183.11
Prob		0.0000	0.0000

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

The results presented in Table 4.7 show a positive and insignificant impact of institutional quality on intra-African trade in ECOWAS. The coefficient of the Institutional Quality Index (IQI), according to the results of OLS, PCSE, and FGLS as shown in Table 4.7, is positive and statistically insignificant on trade in ECOWAS countries at 1%. The same results are found when controlling for omitted variables by country-time fixed effects. The R-squared values indicate that the independent variables explain about 45%, 46% of the behavior of the dependent variable. All the standard errors are robust to autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity.

Table 4.8: Results of OLS, PCSE and FGLS estimates (Robustness Checks)

DISAGGREGATED

Variables	OLS	PCSE	FGLS
VC	.4336221 (0.001)	.3777728 (0.079)	.3777728 (0.001)
RQ	.5085741 (0.004)	.58446246 (0.062)	.5846246 (0.000)
PS	-.161982 (0.036)	-.1130859 (0.402)	-.1130859 (0.104)
GOV	-.3548282 (0.020)	-.3710332 (0.189)	-.3710332 (0.007)
CORR	-.2397954 (0.052)	-.3054257 (0.145)	-.3054257 (0.006)
RULE	.1057002 (0.532)	.1456413 (0.645)	.1456413 (0.353)
GDP	.0526811 (0.812)	.1280278 (0.443)	.1280278 (0.506)
GDPpc	.0011798 (0.526)	.0015224 (0.647)	.0015224 (0.388)
POP	-13.70446 (0.000)	.0015224 (0.001)	.0015224 (0.000)
DIST	-.0031492 (0.342)	-.0024857 (0.482)	-.0024857 (0.422)
LANDLOCK	5.767966 (0.078)	6.617652 (0.286)	6.617652 (0.027)
LANG	1.871699 (0.345)	1.9715151 (0.628)	1.9715151 (0.295)
R ²	0.5295	0.5333	
Wald chi ²		57.34	239.97
Prob		0.0000	0.0000

Source: Author's computation using output from Stata 15

Examining the robustness of the overall results presented in Table 4.8, it could be concluded that the model is robust to all post-estimation tests irrespective of the technique adopted, as revealed by R-squared and the Wald chi-squared values. The R-squared values indicate that the independent variables

explain about 45%, 46% of the behavior of the dependent variable. All the standard errors are robust to autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity.

4.5 Evaluation of Research Hypothesis

4.5.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Institutional quality has no significant impact on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS member states.

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the probability value of institutional quality is less than 0.05. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is not to be rejected at a 5 percent level of significance.

Conclusion: The result presented in tables 4.4 & 4.5 shows the probability values of institutional quality index is less than 0.05 percent level of significant ($P(t) = 0.439 < 0.05$) in the aggregated analysis table, whereas, the probability value of institutional quality indicators is less than 0.05 percent level of significant ($P(t) = 0.000, 0.000, 0.002, 0.001, 0.001 > 0.05$). Therefore, we can conclude that the institutional quality index has no significant effect on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS, while it has significant effect on bilateral trade in ECOWAS countries in disaggregated analysis.

4.5.2 Test of Hypothesis two

H₀₂: Institutional quality does not facilitate intra-regional trade among ECOWAS member state.

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis if the probability value of institutional quality is less than 0.05. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is not to be rejected at 5 percent level of significant.

Conclusion: The result presented in tables 4.4 & 4.5 shows the probability values of institutional quality index is less than 0.05 percent level of significant ($P(t) = 0.439 < 0.05$) in the aggregated analysis table, whereas, the probability value of institutional quality indicators is less than 0.05 percent level of significant ($P(t) = 0.000, 0.000, 0.002, 0.001, 0.001 > 0.05$). Therefore, we can conclude that institutional quality index has positive insignificant effect on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS, while it has positive significant effect on bilateral trade in ECOWAS countries. This implies that institutional quality indicators encourage intra-regional trade among ECOWAS countries.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the effects of institutional quality on intra-regional commerce in ECOWAS using six institutional quality datasets and an enhanced gravity model. The Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimate technique was used in the study, which used balanced panel data from 15 ECOWAS countries over a 13-year period of 2010–2023. The World Development Measures database provided the study with yearly data on institutional quality measures, including legislative efficacy, political stability, voice and accountability, regulatory quality, rule of law, and corruption control. The CEPII database included additional explanatory factors, while the World Bank's WITS provided statistics on bilateral trade. The study showed that three out of six indicators of institutional quality had

a positive and significant effect on trade, while the other three had a negative but significant impact on bilateral trade in ECOWAS.

However, under aggregate analysis institutional quality index had a positive but insignificant impact on trade. ECOWAS countries' bilateral trade flows are also found to be significantly influenced by the traditional gravity model variables, which include GDP, GDP per capita, bilateral distance, common border, common official language, and landlocked. The results indicated that GDP and GDP per capita have an insignificant positive impact on bilateral trade across ECOWAS region. Also, population growth was found to be negative but significant in determining bilateral trade in ECOWAS. The result further revealed that distance had an insignificant negative impact on bilateral trade in ECOWAS countries. Finally, there existed a uni-directional causality association flow from institutional quality to intra-regional trade.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffered:

Given that three of six institutional quality indicators have a negative but significant impact on intra-regional trade in ECOWAS,

- i. Policymakers in ECOWAS should improve their institutional frameworks to combat corruption, political instability, and enhance government effectiveness through measures such as relaxed licensing requirements, reduced import taxes, and other bureaucratic bottlenecks.
- ii. Since both aggregated and disaggregated analyses show a significant impact of institutional quality on bilateral trade, each ECOWAS member should invest in country-specific governance reforms such as improving contract enforcement, reducing bureaucratic red tape, and strengthening the rule of law.

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